

UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS IN THE TEACHING OF GENETICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OGBIA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BAYELSA STATE

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18291483>

Abstract

The study examined the utilization of artificial intelligence tools in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design for the study. The population for the study comprised 104 Biology teachers from the public secondary schools in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled "Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Teaching of Genetics Questionnaire (UAIITGQ)". The instrument was validated by three research experts and the reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method. The reliability yielded 0.81 for cluster 1 and 0.79 for cluster 2 with a reliability estimate of 0.80 which made it reliable. The statistical tools used for this study were mean and standard deviation for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic. The findings of the study revealed that BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine were utilized to a very low extent in teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. The study recommended among others that secondary schools should increase the integration of BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine into genetics instruction to enhance students' understanding and engagement.

Keywords: Utilization, Artificial Intelligence Tools, Genetics, BioDigital Human, Google Teachable Machine

Introduction

Biology is the branch of science that studies living organisms and their life processes. Biology is the scientific study of living organisms and how they function, grow, evolve, and interact with their environment (Campbell & Reece, 2017). It examines life at all levels, from molecules and cells to whole ecosystems and the diversity of species (Raven et al., 2020). The field also investigates the genetic, physiological, and ecological processes that support life. By using observation, experimentation, and analysis, biology generates knowledge that is

vital for medicine, conservation, and biotechnology. Biology studies the structure, function, growth, and evolution of living organisms, providing the foundation for understanding how traits are passed, variations occur, and heredity is explained, culminating in genetics.

Genetics is the branch of biology that focuses on the study of genes, heredity, and the variations observed in living organisms (Griffiths et al., 2015). It investigates how traits and characteristics are inherited from parents to offspring through DNA sequences.

The field also explores the processes of gene expression, mutation, and genetic recombination (Pierce, 2017). A clear understanding of genetics is essential for making progress in medicine, agriculture, and the study of evolution. In many secondary schools and universities, genetics is usually taught through the traditional lecture method, where teachers explain concepts while students listen and take notes (Campbell & Reece, 2017). This method often results in low student engagement and makes it difficult for learners to fully understand complex topics like gene expression and inheritance, leading to poorer academic performance. Studies by Byukusenge et al. (2021) showed that students struggle to visualize genetic processes and apply theoretical knowledge, which negatively impacts their learning outcomes. Incorporating modern technologies and interactive tools like artificial intelligence, especially artificial intelligence, may significantly improve students' comprehension and performance in genetics.

Artificial intelligence (AI) tools are software systems designed to mimic human intelligence, allowing machines to perform tasks such as problem-solving, learning, reasoning, and decision-making (Russell & Norvig, 2021). They are capable of processing large amounts of data, identifying patterns, and making predictions with minimal human intervention (Goodfellow et al., 2016). AI tools are used in many areas, including education, healthcare, business, and research, to improve efficiency and accuracy (Shabbir & Anwer, 2018). In education, these tools help personalize learning by adapting content to the needs of

individual students and offering real-time feedback. They also enable data analysis, virtual simulations, and intelligent tutoring systems that enhance understanding and retention. AI tools provide a transformative way to solve problems and support learning, making complex tasks easier and outcomes more effective. BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine are the main AI tools considered in this study.

BioDigital Human is a cloud-based interactive 3D platform that allows users to explore a virtual map of the human body, including detailed anatomy, physiological systems, diseases, and treatments, making it a reliable resource for medical education (Egbunu, 2024). Its anatomical models are medically accurate, built from surgical and dissection data, imaging like MRI and CT scans, and expert-reviewed atlases, helping learners visualize structures that are difficult to grasp through textbooks or 2D diagrams. Google Teachable Machine is a web-based AI tool that allows users, even without coding experience, to create machine-learning models that recognize images, sounds, or human poses (Usman & Bello, 2025). Users can train classifiers directly in the browser by uploading examples and organizing them into classes, making machine learning accessible and intuitive.

The trained models can be exported and integrated into websites or applications, enabling practical applications like image recognition, pose detection, and sound classification. Both tools demonstrate how interactive and AI-based technologies enhance learning and engagement by providing personalized, visual, and hands-on experiences. Egbunu (2024) observed that

many biology teachers in Abuja rarely use advanced digital tools beyond basic resources due to limited awareness and training, while Bello and Atotileto (2025) similarly reported minimal utilization of AI tools in science instruction nationwide. Likewise, the use of Google Teachable Machine in teaching genetics was found to be very limited, supporting findings by Abiola and Ajayi (2024) and Usman and Bello (2025), who highlighted low awareness and practice of AI tools among teachers and students in various regions. These studies collectively suggest that inadequate infrastructure, lack of teacher preparedness, and low awareness continue to impede the effective integration of advanced AI-based educational tools in Nigerian secondary school biology teachers.

Biology teachers are specialized educators who teach biological sciences, including the study of living organisms and their structure, functions, and interactions, using the principles of life (Campbell & Reece, 2017). Their duties include lesson plan development, conducting experiments, and managing theoretical and practical student learning in a classroom or laboratory setting (Akpan, 2018). Biology teachers also evaluate students' knowledge, conduct scientific investigations, and motivate them to pursue scientific research and problem-solving. Their role is quite important in shaping the knowledge, attitude, and skills of students toward science, thus future academic and career options in the biological sciences. Studies show that male biology teachers are generally more likely to use advanced technologies and AI tools when teaching genetics than their female colleagues, reflecting a disparity shaped by differences in access, confidence, and training in gender.

Gender is defined as the social, cultural, and psychological attributes, roles, and behaviors that society deems appropriate for both men and women. It is also distinguished from biological sex (Butler, 2019). It is related to identity, expression, and societal expectations, which are influenced by the type of opportunities, interactions, and experiences one encounters in various situations. Gender determines personal and social development, including education, career options, and contributions in various societal settings. Understanding gender is critical to addressing inequalities, promoting inclusivity, and ensuring equitable policies and practices in schools and beyond, especially in relation to the low rate at which AI tools are utilized.

The low rate at which AI tools such as BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine are being utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia LGA concerns the researchers. This should be ideal in bringing interactive, visually enriched lessons that enhance students' understanding, retention, and practical skills in genetics. However, most of them lack awareness and training on these technologies, hence adopting traditional methods of lecturing that limit students' engagement in understanding the subject. This has led to underutilization, eventually dragging down students' performance and hindering the development of 21st-century skills, hence compromising the overall effectiveness of genetic education in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal educational environment, all secondary school teachers in Ogbia Local Government Area would utilize advanced technology tools to enhance student

understanding of complex topics in genetics. Blended integration of AI tools such as BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine would allow teachers to provide interactive, visually enriched content to make the abstractions in genetics more accessible and appealing for learners. This would lead to active participation by students during the lesson, increased retention of genetic knowledge, and practical skills developed through simulation experiments. Utilization will help in ensuring that teachers also benefit in their professional growth through the use of modern pedagogical approaches and technology-enhanced instructional methods. This can be an ideal place where technology bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical understanding in genetics education.

But in reality, the use of such AI tools in genetics teaching in Ogbia secondary schools remains very low. Many teachers are not aware and are not equipped through training with the use of BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine; hence, they fall back on traditional lectures that limit students' involvement and thus lower their understanding. Students, therefore, fail to understand such complex genetic concepts, leading to poor academic performance of the students and reducing interest in the science-related subjects. Besides, underutilization of the said tools has hindered the acquisition of 21st-century skills among learners and innovative practices of teaching among educators. If not checked, both teaching quality and the learning outcomes of students in genetics will continue to stagnate, hence compromising the overall effectiveness of science education in the region.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the utilization of artificial intelligence tools in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State;
2. Ascertain the extent to which Google Teachable Machine is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent is BioDigital Human utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent is Google Teachable Machine utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which **Google**

Teachable Machine is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Research Method

The researchers adopted a descriptive survey research design for this study. According to Nassaji (2015), a descriptive survey is a systematic method by which one seeks to accurately describe the characteristics or behaviour of members of particular group without controlling variables. The population for the study comprised 104 Biology teachers from the public secondary schools in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled “Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Teaching of Genetics Questionnaire (UAIITGQ)”.

The instrument was validated by three research experts and the reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method. The reliability yielded 0.81 for cluster 1 and 0.79 for cluster 2 with a reliability estimate of 0.80 which made it reliable. The researcher used mean scores, cluster mean and standard deviation in answering the five research questions. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: VHE = 3.50-4.00; HE = 2.50-3.49; LE = 1.50-2.49; VLE = 0.00-1.49. t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypothesis was not rejected when the probability values are less or equal to 0.05, but was rejected when the probability values are greater than 0.05.

Results and Data Presentation

Research Question 1: To what extent is BioDigital Human utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics

ITEMS		Male Biology Teachers			Female Biology Teachers		
S/N	BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics to the following extent:	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.
1.	using BioDigital Human regularly to explain genetic concepts	1.05	0.50	VLE	1.03	0.49	VLE
2.	integrating BioDigital Human visuals in classroom teaching	1.00	0.46	VLE	1.02	0.47	VLE
3.	assigning students tasks using BioDigital Human simulations	1.02	0.48	VLE	1.01	0.46	VLE
4.	using BioDigital Human to demonstrate complex genetic processes	1.04	0.45	VLE	1.02	0.48	VLE
5.	referring to BioDigital Human in assessments or quizzes	1.01	0.47	VLE	1.00	0.46	VLE
6.	encouraging students to explore BioDigital Human independently	1.03	0.48	VLE	1.03	0.47	VLE
Cluster Mean/SD		1.03	0.47	VLE	1.02	0.47	VLE

The table shows that both male and female Biology teachers utilize BioDigital Human in teaching genetics to a very low extent. Male teachers had a cluster mean of 1.03 with a standard deviation of 0.47, while females had a cluster mean of 1.02 with a standard deviation of 0.47. The lowest use was found in integrating BioDigital Human visuals,

with means of 1.00 for males and 1.02 for females. The highest use was in regularly using BioDigital Human to explain genetic concepts and demonstrating complex genetic processes, with means ranging from 1.03 to 1.05. Overall, the findings indicate minimal engagement with BioDigital Human across all the measured teaching activities.

Research Question 2: To what extent is Google Teachable Machine utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which Google Teachable Machine is utilized in the teaching of genetics

S/N	ITEMS	Male Biology Teachers			Female Biology Teachers		
		\bar{x}	SD	Dec.	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.
	Google Teachable Machine is utilized in the teaching of genetics to the following extent:						
7.	using Google Teachable Machine to create genetic simulations for lessons	1.04	0.47	VLE	1.05	0.46	VLE
8.	allowing students to interact with Google Teachable Machine during class activities	1.05	0.46	VLE	1.07	0.45	VLE
9.	incorporating Google Teachable Machine outputs in teaching complex genetics concepts	1.06	0.45	VLE	1.06	0.44	VLE
10.	assessing students' understanding using Google Teachable Machine exercises	1.03	0.46	VLE	1.05	0.46	VLE
11.	referring students to explore Google Teachable Machine for independent learning	1.05	0.47	VLE	1.06	0.45	VLE
12.	integrating Google Teachable Machine outputs in classroom presentations	1.06	0.46	VLE	1.06	0.45	VLE
	Cluster Mean/SD	1.05	0.46	VLE	1.06	0.45	VLE

As seen from the table, male and female Biology teachers use Google Teachable Machine in teaching genetics to a very low extent. For male teachers, the cluster mean was 1.05 with a standard deviation of 0.46, while for female teachers, the cluster mean was 1.06 with a standard deviation of 0.45. The lowest utilization for males was in assessing students' understanding through Google Teachable Machine exercises at 1.03,

while that of females was in using the tool to create genetic simulations at 1.05. The highest utilization was seen in incorporating outputs of Google Teachable Machine in teaching complex concepts and classroom presentations, where the means for males and females were 1.06 each. Overall, results indicate very minimal integration of Google Teachable Machine in classroom teaching and student activities.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 3: t-test on the mean scores in the perceptions of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which BioDigital Human is utilized in the teaching of genetics

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	46	1.03	0.47	102	0.914	H0 ₁ not rejected
Female	58	1.02	0.47			

The table indicates the mean utilization of BioDigital Human by male and female Biology teachers to be 1.03 and 1.02, respectively, with a standard deviation of 0.47. Using an independent samples t-test, we obtained a t-value corresponding to a p-value of 0.914. As the p-value is greater than 0.05, H0₁ (the null hypothesis) cannot be rejected. It can therefore be deduced that there is no significant difference between the utilization of BioDigital Human by male and female teachers in teaching genetics.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which **Google Teachable Machine** is utilized in the teaching of genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Table 4: t-test on the mean scores in the perceptions of male and female Biology teachers on the extent to which **Google Teachable Machine** is utilized in the teaching of genetics

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	46	1.05	0.46	102	0.912	H0 ₂ not rejected
Female	58	1.06	0.45			

From the table, it can be seen that male Biology teachers had an average utilization of Google Teachable Machine of 1.05, while female teachers utilized the technology at an average rate of 1.06, with standard deviations of 0.46 and 0.45, respectively. The t-test yielded a p-value of 0.912. Because the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H0₂) should not be rejected. This means that no significant difference has been detected between male and female teachers in the extent to which they use Google Teachable Machine in teaching genetics.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study indicated that BioDigital Human was used to a very low extent in the teaching of genetics in Ogbia LGA of Bayelsa State. The findings are also consistent with Egbunu (2024), in which it was established that many biology teachers in Abuja rarely used any advanced digital tool outside basic resources due to lack of awareness and training. Similarly, Bello and Atotileto (2025) found that the use of AI tools was also very limited in science instruction in Nigerian secondary schools. It appears from these related studies that systemic constraints on infrastructure, access to resources, and lack of preparedness of teachers impede the

effective usage of advanced digital tools. Thus, the very low utilization of BioDigital Human in Ogbia Secondary Schools reflects what obtains nationally in the integration of technology into science education.

This study found that the usage of Google Teachable Machine in teaching genetics was very minimal in these schools. This supports Abiola and Ajayi 2024, who found that the majority of biology teachers in Ilorin, Kwara State, showed low awareness and practice of using generative AI tools to conduct lessons. Similarly, Usman and Bello 2025 found that students in Lere, Kaduna State, had extremely low awareness and utilization of AI tools, including machine learning applications, in learning biology. These studies suggest that even though AI-enabled tools like Google Teachable Machine are available, the actual usage in teaching remains very low. This relatively low utilization is consistent with broader trends in Nigerian secondary school biology education due to various factors such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and general low awareness.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study revealed that BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine were used to a very low extent in teaching genetics in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. This limited use indicates that teachers are not yet exploring all the possibilities of new digital tools to support the teaching of genetics. This low usage also reflects gaps in the digital competences of teachers and access to supportive infrastructure. These deficiencies diminish students' opportunities to have interactive and technology-enhanced

learning experiences in genetics. The findings, therefore, identify the need for targeted training, improved ICT resources, and policy support in a bid to enhance adoption of innovative tools of this kind. The study concludes that strengthening digital integration is essential for improving the quality of genetics teaching in this area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Biology teachers should go through practical training for integrating BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine into genetics lessons.
2. Secondary schools in Bayelsa State should be equipped with computers, tablets, projectors, and stable internet connectivity. These facilities will provide the opportunity for teachers to adopt technology-based instructional resources.
3. Secondary schools should increase the integration of BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine into genetics instruction to enhance students' understanding and engagement.
4. BioDigital Human and Google Teachable Machine should be mandated and supported by education authorities for use in teaching genetics. This will foster regular adoption and increases students' comprehension of abstract ideas related to genetics.

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